

DIPLOMA

TA'LIM FIDOYILARI

RESPUBLIKA ILMIY JURNALIDA

Ibragimova Shoira Abdunabievna

SWIMMING AND A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

Bosh muharrir:
A.A. Abdurahmonov

2023/APREL

YOUR SEAL